

Comparing different GPS solutions for the Cooperative Awareness Messages Distribution

Carlo Augusto Grazia, Martin Klapez, and Maurizio Casoni

Abstract—Cooperative awareness messages (CAM) are a family standardized by ETSI to distribute relevant information to all the nodes in vehicle coverage, such as time, position, speed, direction, etc. The parameters needed to trigger these messages, as well as the information contained in the messages themselves, can be obtained with a GPS receiver. Our paper aims to increase the efficiency of CAM generation and dissemination in a less-is-more style, considering different GPS devices of different qualities. We achieve this goal by comparing the effectiveness of two GPS, belonging to two different market segments, with an order of magnitude of a price gap between them. We compared them in two different scenarios, similar in layout and traffic behavior but different in terms of GPS coverage conditions.

Field trials with DSRC IEEE 802.11p have been carried out in an urban environment where different GPS coverage conditions widely emerge, with the possible presence of large buildings that emphasize all the GPS challenges: reducing the number of visible GPS satellites, introducing multi-path effects, fading, and reducing the signal strength.

While having some notable differences in the two scenarios, we found the triggers' distributions to be similar between both the receiver devices. Instead, the average time between consecutive awareness messages has been found to be significantly lower in the case of bad coverage compared with the open-sky scenario, something that may reflect the presence of unwanted messages triggered by the GPS errors rather than the real vehicle motion. Therefore, we designed a new CAM generation algorithm that also considers the GPS error to reduce the messages transmitted on the radio medium.

Index Terms—CAM, DSRC/IEEE 802.11p, Field Trials, V2X

I. INTRODUCTION

The role of wireless communications in the Intelligent Transportation System (ITS) picture is crucial for designing safe road environments, especially in urban scenarios with frequent Non-Line-Of-Sight (NLOS) circumstances. The interest has been mainly focused on vehicular communications that rely on either IEEE 802.11p or Long-Term Evolution (LTE) Vehicle-To-Everything (LTE-V2X). Their evolutions were recently presented through IEEE 802.11bd and 5G New Radio Cellular V2X (NR C-V2X), respectively [1]. The IEEE 802.11p Wireless Access for Vehicular Environments (WAVE)

is a collection of amendments pertaining to vehicular settings made to the IEEE 802.11-2012 standard [2] (now superseded by the IEEE 802.11-2016 standard [3]). The latter is the basis for the so-called Dedicated Short-Range Communications (DSRC). DSRC was envisioned to operate similarly to a network used for emergency communications, but while the aim of the latter is often to restore communications in areas where infrastructure is damaged by using a backhaul channel [4], [5], DSRC enables from the onset both vehicle-to-vehicle and vehicle-to-infrastructure communications to propagate safety information automatically. In fact, it was originally designed to enable collision-prevention applications [6], but the interest in V2X transmissions quickly spread to encompass consumer-centric services like entertainment, traffic data, navigation, and also autonomous driving. Traditionally more focused on the latter uses, C-V2X has emerged as a competing technology with its own strong points as, for instance, the leverage of cellular infrastructures and the coverage of larger areas by single radio items. The two technologies have been compared in multiple studies, e.g., in [7], [8], and their coexistence has also been hypothesized and investigated [9].

Vehicular awareness messages are standardized at the application layer and are independent of the access technology (e.g., C-V2X or IEEE 802.11p) [10], [11]. The idea for vehicles is to broadcast these messages in order to reach every node in the area of coverage, distributing relevant attributes like position, speed, course over ground, etc. According to the ETSI terminology, we deal with Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAMs), and both the way these messages are generated, as well as the content of the messages themselves, strongly depends on the GPS receiver on board the vehicle, used to infer the vehicle position, acceleration, speed, and course over ground.

This work compares a campaign on real data collected by a car equipped with two different GPS receivers in two similar urban scenarios, compliant with the guidelines of the Car2Car consortium in [12]. The key difference between the two scenarios is the GPS coverage condition, which in one case suffers the presence of buildings and canyoning effects, while in the other case, benefits from open-sky conditions that ease the work of GPS receivers. The two GPS receivers onboard belong to two different groups, according to their quality and price, and have been widely tested in applications involving the automotive domain [13]. It is important to notice that since our paper looks at the generation pattern at the application level, it is independent of the technology deployed, either C-V2X or IEEE 802.11p. All the results collected are GPS-based and treated in a post-processing fashion. We then followed the ETSI algorithms formalized in [10] to identify

M. Klapez, C.A. Grazia, and M. Casoni are with the Department of Engineering *Enzo Ferrari*, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, via Pietro Vivarelli, 10, 41125, Modena, Italy (e-mail: {martin.klapez, carloaugusto.grazia, maurizio.casoni}@unimore.it).

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the awareness messages triggered by the GPS traces with the proper timing, proposing an evolution to the algorithm that considers the GPS signal quality.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II briefly overviews related works. Section III introduces the role of GPS in CAM dissemination, the core of our investigation. Section IV describes the equipment utilized, its configuration, and its field setup. Section V presents and analyzes the results while Section VI concludes the article.

II. RELATED WORKS

Example of papers that recently focused on cooperative awareness messages are here reported. The study described in [14] employs field tests to validate CAMs and Decentralized Environmental Notification Messages (DENMs) capabilities through several performance indicators, while [15] also investigates the influence of external variables, such as vehicle speed, Line-Of-Sight (LOS), or message dissemination rules, on the performance in the dissemination of CAMs and DENMs. Similarly, [16] employs field tests and large-scale simulations to explore the practical limits of cooperative awareness in both Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) transmissions, in which the infrastructure is not involved, and Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I) transmissions. Due to the time of their writing, these works do not consider the LTE-V2X technology but communications based on IEEE 802.11p instead.

Regarding the latter, [17] reports field tests that, in terms of road shape, path length, and investigated metrics, are similar to our preliminary mobility tests presented in [18], although they are conducted at lower speeds. In [19], we presented a methodology to study packet collision interference due to the hidden terminal problem, while in [20] we studied the technology in high-speed trials. Also with a focus on highway communications, [21] experimentally compares ITS-G5 and LTE-V2X in terms of PDR and latency.

Still concerning CAMs, there are no literature contributions investigating how GPS affects V2X applications based on cooperative messages. However, it is clear from the literature that the GPS requirements are different from one application to another, as well as the impact of GPS errors, which is significant for CAMs, where GPS data are both the input and the output of the mechanism.

The work [22] classifies the possible GPS measurements in classes of accuracy based on the measure itself, the environmental conditions, and the classes of accuracy that the applications require. Unfortunately, a numerical example to estimate the GPS quality is not provided. The GPS accuracy requirements for V2X applications is also investigated in [23], where CAMs are classified in the application group that requires “relative” positioning rather than absolute, indeed, the relative variation of position of a vehicle (and between vehicles) is the condition that triggers the messages. In [24] is analyzed how much a misbehaving vehicle affects the global performance of V2X applications and how hard is to detect false alarms. This work highlight, in a sense, the importance to avoid false CAM triggers by dealing with the GPS error. For what concern, instead, the evaluation of different GPS

receivers in the automotive domain, the authors in [13] tested circa 20 GPS of three quality categories in several conditions. This work has been useful in selecting the pair of GPS receiver to design our test campaign. Continuing, even the work [25] claims that very little research has been conducted to evaluate the impacts of positioning accuracy on V2X applications; indeed, this paper’s goal is to examine the effect of the positioning error in specific applications with a simplified environment. Unfortunately, CAMs are not considered in the applications covered by the analysis. Concluding, different possible location systems, including accuracy and numbers for GPS, but also potential alternatives for the automotive domain is reported in [26].

III. THE ROLE OF GPS

Cooperative awareness messages require GPS signals to feed the algorithm that triggers the CAMs generation. GPS data is required for both the input and the output since the localization parameters are used for triggering conditions and then disseminated as well. A complete NMEA string that contains all the relevant information to generate CAM effectively is the Recommended Minimum Specific GNSS Data (RMC), available as output from almost all commercial GPS devices. The RMC string contains a timestamp, latitude, longitude, speed, and Course Over Ground (COG). We will refer to the latter also under the name of heading, which is the word used in [27] to indicate the direction of a vehicle motion. At the same time, the COG is obtained as the angle computed as the straight line which connects to consecutive GPS samples, and it is not an instantaneous value for implementation restriction.

Since the GPS role in the CAM computation is critical, we designed a metric that, from the sole RMC data, is able to detect a reduction of the GPS signal quality and a potential localization imprecision. This metric is based on how speed and location are computed by the receiver. The speed reported by the GPS receiver is typically computed using the Doppler shift of the signals received from GPS satellites. The GPS receiver is able to detect and measure the shift in the frequency of the signals caused by the relative motion between the receiver and the satellites. By comparing the frequencies of the received signals with the known frequencies of the signals transmitted by the satellites, the receiver can calculate its velocity relative to the satellites. This velocity is then used to compute the speed over ground of the receiver’s movement. On the other hand, the position reported by the GPS receiver is typically computed using a process called trilateration, which involves measuring the distance between the receiver and multiple GPS satellites. We define a variable Δ_s computed from each sample $i > 1$ that collects the speed in two different ways, extracting the module between the two values. It is computed as follows:

$$\Delta_{s_i} = \left| \frac{V_{RMC_{i-1}} + V_{RMC_i}}{2} - \frac{hd(p_{i-1}, p_i)}{t_i - t_{i-1}} \right|. \quad (1)$$

Where V_{RMC_i} is the speed written in the RMC string, and the $hd()$ function computes the Haversine distance between the position of two consecutive RMC samples. In other words, Δ_{s_i}

Short Name	Model / Chipset	Rate [Hz]	Constellation	NMEA String	IMU
u8	NEO-M8U UDR	10	GPS + GLONASS	GPRMC	yes
u7	VK-162	10	GPS	GPRMC	no

TABLE I: Measurement result of Exp.1

Fig. 1: Mikrotik evaluation board (RB912UAG-5HPND) used for the field measurements.

registers the absolute difference between the average speed reported in two consecutive RMC samples and the speed computed as the covered distance over time between two consecutive samples.

Cooperative Awareness Messages: The ETSI standard dictates the CAM generation times under the following conditions, all starting from the last CAM transmitted at time t_1 , with position p_1 , heading h_1 , and speed s_1 , and the time t_n which corresponds to the last RMC sample registered with position p_n , heading h_n and speed s_n :

- (i) If $(t_n - t_1) > T_{GenCamMax}$.
- (ii) If the euclidean distance $|p_n - p_1| > \Delta_d = 4$ m.
- (iii) If the heading angle $|h_n - h_1| > \Delta_h = 4^\circ$
- (iv) If the speed difference $s_n - s_1 > \Delta_s = 0.5$ m/s.

We remind the reader that $T_{GenCamMax}$ is imposed at 1 second by the standard; indeed, the lower bound frequency for CAM transmission is 1Hz, and the upper bound is 10Hz.

The thresholds Δ_d , Δ_h , and Δ_s are standardized as fixed. The CAM size is standardized, but not to a specific value; in fact, it can range between 45 and 400 bytes [28]. This fact points to a second free variable to model congestion when dealing with CAMs. Indeed, the non-fixed size of the messages can severely impact channel congestion, considering the range of one entire order of magnitude. Moreover, the message size can also increase after introducing security features, like authentication or integrity, as described in [27]. Instead of tackling any arbitrary CAM implementation profile, this work concentrates on their temporal patterns, collecting important feedback on the average time between different CAMs to model the channel congestion in future simulation environments.

Fig. 2: Open-sky scenario: 44°40'26"N 10°56'12"E.

The idea behind our work is simple since CAMs generation focuses on the relative changes from one GPS sample to another. It is the relative error, and not the absolute one, which affects the generation of erroneous messages. Inferring the absolute error is a hard task, multiple contributions in the literature focused on this challenging problem, but we believe inferring a potential relative error is possible with Δ_s . Indeed, a high Δ_s means that the GPS receiver is computing two different values of speed by measuring it in two different ways, leading to a position error from the previous sample.

IV. FIELD SETUP AND SCENARIOS

The experimental results presented in this section were obtained employing the commercially available MikroTik RB912UAG-5HPnD in Figure 1. This board is flushed with a Linux kernel version 4.4.153 with the ath9k driver, with the goal of configuring an open-source IEEE 802.11p at a 5.9 GHz band with a 10 MHz wide channel. We used the MikroTik board to collect data from two GPS receivers reported in Table I. Both the GPS receivers allow for the detection of Recommended Minimum Data (RMC messages of standard u-blox satellite devices) messages to have access to relevant information like position (latitude and longitude), speed, and course over ground. Throughout these data, it is possible to estimate CAM messages in post-processing, making our test campaign independent from the V2X access technology.

The board was configured to collect GPS data with both the receivers at a frequency of 10Hz, saving the results in a log file that was then accessible for post-processing elaboration. The data have then been cleaned, excluding non-relevant information (e.g., the path to reach the test starting point, the outliers samples due to GPS receiver errors, and non-relevant samples collected just before shutting down the board).

We run our tests in two different scenarios depicted in Figures 2 and 3. Both the scenarios are composed of a

Fig. 3: Canyon scenario: 44°38'32"N 10°56'05"E..

Fig. 4: Δ_s Open-sky

Fig. 5: Δ_s Canyon

Fig. 6: Δ_s comparison

square-shaped circuit of 750 meters of square side; the main significant difference between the two is that the first, depicted in Figure 2, can be considered an open-sky environment, with clear sky vision for the GPS receivers, while the second, depicted in Figure 3, has several portions of the path with limited sky visibility and canyoning effects for the GPS receivers. We did the same car journey five times per scenario for statistical reasons.

V. TEST RESULTS

This section details the test results of GPS samples collected and CAMs generated, in post-processing, by a vehicle on both the scenarios under test. All the first results are computed with the standard CAMs thresholds of $\Delta_d = 4$ m, $\Delta_h = 4^\circ$, and $\Delta_s = 0.5$ m/s.

We first investigated the possibility of considering Δ_s as a metric of GPS accuracy with both receivers in the two investigated scenarios. The results are reported in Figures 4 and 5 for the good and bad coverage scenarios, respectively. Both the figures report the measured Δ_s by u7 and u8, as well as the relative distance, computed as the Haversine distance between RMC samples of u7 and u8 with the same timestamps, reported in red. As expected, the relative distance error between u7 and u8 is higher in the bad-coverage scenario, and error peaks correspond to the Δ_s peaks for both the GPS devices.

We also collected the values of Δ_s as statistical candlesticks in Figure 6, including all the five runs of each test, distinguishing between the two possible scenarios, Open (good-

coverage) and Canyon (bad-coverage), and the two possible GPS devices u7 and u8. Each candle box reports the 10-th and 90-th percentiles, while the solid black line represents the medium value of the numerical sequence of each test. As an output of Figure 6, we defined a Δ_s threshold of 0.5 m/s as the value that is never reached in the good coverage condition and always reached in all the bad coverage runs.

If we post-process the data acquired with a standard CAM algorithm, what we obtain is a pattern of CAM generation which is reported in Figures 7 and 8 for good and bad coverage scenarios, respectively. The possible conditions that may trigger the generation of a CAM are:

- Timeout: corresponding to condition (i) of section III.
- Distance: corresponding to condition (ii) of section III.
- Heading: corresponding to condition (iii) of section III.
- Speed: corresponding to condition (iv) of section III.
- Mixed: more than one of the above are simultaneously satisfied.

Despite the similar characteristics, in terms of layout, between the two scenarios, the CAMs pattern of Figures 7 and 8 is significantly different. According to our tests, the average value of T_{CAM} is higher than 400 ms in good coverage and lower than 300 ms in bad coverage. Such a difference, justified by a different distribution shape and the presence of more *velocity* and *heading* triggers in the left part of Figure 8, holds for both the GPS receiver, which triggered the messages almost equally moving from a scenario to another, and from a run to another,

Fig. 7: CAM triggers and T_{CAM} PMF: Open-sky

Fig. 8: CAM triggers and T_{CAM} PMF: Canyon

not reported here for space constraints but available in our repository [29]. The CAMs distribution of Figure 8 deserves to be analyzed and investigated because the lower T_{CAM} is trivially associated with a higher transmission frequency of CAM messages on the channel, reaching congestion situations with a lower amount of vehicles when the CAM algorithm is in place in bad coverage scenarios. We want to show that the different CAMs distribution comes from fake or unwanted triggers, which are triggered due to GPS errors and not by real vehicle movements. To do so, we also plotted a map-based trigger distribution, where we do not focus on the time between CAM triggers/messages but on where they occur, considering the path as a ground truth regarding vehicle behavior.

Figures 9 and 10 report these map-based triggers for good and bad coverage scenarios, respectively. Figure 9 is easy to be interpreted, where the *velocity* and *heading* triggers occur almost exclusively in the corner, where the speed change approaching and escaping from the turns, and the COG (angle) changes traveling them. Other *velocity* triggers correspond to the place in which the test is started and stopped, where again the speed changes with accelerations and breaks, respectively. Where the speed is constant, and the path is straight, only *position* CAMs are triggered on the four straight roads of the square. On the other side, Figure 10 is not justified straightforwardly as the previous one. Some *velocity* triggers on the straight roads are justified by the presence of stop signals for cross-roads, but all the *heading* triggers that are not on the corners are not justified by the vehicle behavior, which moved in a straight line on each straight road.

To mitigate the effect of fake triggers, we designed a new CAM generation algorithm called Featherweight CAM

Fig. 9: CAM triggers on map: Open-sky

Fig. 10: CAM triggers on map: Canyon

(FCAM), which also considers Δ_s in the process. If Δ_s is higher than 0.5 m/s, we know that the GPS signal quality is bad and is potentially affecting the precision of, in particular, *heading* and *velocity* triggers. The FCAM algorithm doubles the threshold of CAM generation for both *heading* and *velocity*, from $\Delta_h = 4^\circ$ to $\Delta_h = 8^\circ$ and from $\Delta_s = 0.5$ m/s to $\Delta_s = 1$ m/s. Moreover, this threshold increment is maintained for 10 seconds because, on high Δ_s , the GPS receiver requires a sensible amount of samples to recover from error conditions. The results of changing the CAM algorithm in FCAM are reported in Figure 11, which compared to Figure 10 immediately reports almost clean straights, with *heading* and *velocity* triggers maintained in the corners. Moreover, Figure 12 reports the CAMs distributions with the FCAM algorithm, which has a pattern more similar to the open scenario now, with a smooth distribution and a T_{CAM} on average larger than 400 ms.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work discussed the result obtained during a real-test campaign involving a vehicle equipped with two GPS receiver classes in two different scenarios. The goal has been to collect, process, and compare the GPS traces which are involved in the generation of CAM messages. Analyzing the data collected during the test campaign, we found that the two GPS devices behave similarly, despite the price gap, while it is possible to distinguish between good and bad GPS coverage with both the devices, considering the defined Δ_s metric. We created a new

Fig. 11: FCAM triggers on map: Canyon

Fig. 12: FCAM triggers and T_{CAM} PMF: Canyon

algorithm called FCAM to increase the efficiency of CAM generation and dissemination in a less-is-more style, showing that the FCAM generation pattern in bad coverage is similar to the CAM generation pattern in good coverage, regardless of the GPS receiver, significantly reducing the number of fake triggers, as well as the congestion on the wireless medium. Future works will focus on different Δ_s thresholds with more GPS receivers and scenarios, including also vulnerable road users, in the analysis.

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